

БИМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

9 ЖИЛД, 4 СОН

ЖУРНАЛ БИМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ

ТОМ 9, НОМЕР 4

JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE

VOLUME 9, ISSUE 4

Бош муҳаррир:

Ризаев Жасур Алимжанович
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор,
Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети ректори
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5468-9403

Бош муҳаррир ўринбосари:

Зиядуллаев Шухрат Худайбердиевич
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт
университети Илмий ишлар ва инновациялар бўйича
проректори, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-9309-3933

Масъул котиб:

Самиева Гулноза Утқуровна
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, доцент,
Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6142-7054

Нашр учун масъул:

Шаханова Шахноза Шавкатовна
PhD, Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети,
онкология кафедраси
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-0888-9150

ТАХРИРИЯТ КЕНГАШИ:

Арипова Тамара Уктамовна

*Иммунология ва инсон геномикаси институти директори –
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор, Ўзбекистон
Республикаси Фанлар академияси академиги*

Jin Young Choi

*Сеул миллий университети Стоматология мактаби оғиз ва
юз-жағ жарроҳлиги департаменти профессори, Жанубий
Кореянинг юз-жағ ва эстетик жарроҳлик ассоциацияси
президенти*

Абдуллаева Наргиза Нурмаатовна

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор, Самарқанд
давлат тиббиёт университети проректори, 1-клиникаси бош
врачи. **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-7529-4248*

Худоярова Дилдора Рахимовна

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, доцент, Самарқанд давлат
тиббиёт университети №1-сон Акушерлик ва гинекология
кафедраси мудири
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5770-2255*

Орипов Фирдавс Суръатович

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, доцент, Самарқанд давлат
тиббиёт университети Гистология, цитология ва
эмбриология кафедраси мудири
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-0615-0144*

Мавлянов Фарход Шавкатович

*тиббиёт фандар доктори, Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт
университети болалар жарроҳлиги кафедраси доценти
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2650-4445*

Магзумова Наргиза Махкамовна

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, Тошкент тиббиёт
академияси Оилавий тиббиётда акушерлик ва гинекология
кафедраси профессори **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-9313-4918*

Акбаров Миршавкат Миролимович

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, В.Ваҳидов номидаги
Республика ихтисослаштирилган жарроҳлик маркази*

Саидов Садамир Абборович

*тиббиёт фанлар доктори,
Тошкент фармацевтика институти
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6616-5428*

Бабалжанов Ойбек Абдуҷаббарович

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, Тошкент педиатрия
тиббиёт институти, Тери-таносил, болалар
тери-таносил касалликлари ва ОИТС
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-3022-916X*

Теребаев Билим Алдамуратович

*тиббиёт фанлари номзоди, доцент, Тошкент
педиатрия тиббиёт институти Факультет болалар
хирургия кафедраси. **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-5409-4327*

Юлдашев Ботир Ахматович

*тиббиёт фанлари номзоди,
Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети
№2-сон Педиатрия, неонатология ва болалар
касаликлари пропедевтикаси кафедраси доценти.
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2442-1523*

Ибрагимова Малика Худайбергановна

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор
Тошкент давлат стоматология институти
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9235-1742*

Рахимов Нодир Махамматкулович

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, Самарқанд давлат
тиббиёт университети, онкология кафедраси доценти
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5272-5503*

Саҳифаловчи: Хуршид Мирзахмедов

Контакт редакций журналлов. www.tadqiqot.uz

ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.

Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz

Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz

Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.

Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz

Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

Главный редактор:

Ризаев Жасур Алимджанович
доктор медицинских наук, профессор, Ректор
Самаркандского государственного медицинского
университета, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0001-5468-9403

Заместитель главного редактора:

Зиядуллаев Шухрат Худайбердиевич
доктор медицинских наук, проректор по научной
работе и инновациям Самаркандского государственного
медицинского университета, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-9309-

Ответственный секретарь:

Самиева Гульноза Уткуровна
доктор медицинских наук, доцент Самаркандского
государственного медицинского университета.
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6142-7054

Ответственный за публикацию:

Шаханова Шахноза Шавкатовна
PhD кафедры онкологии Самаркандского
государственного медицинского университета
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-0888-9150

РЕДАКЦИОННЫЙ КОЛЛЕГИЯ:

Арипова Тамара Уктамовна

директор Института иммунологии и геномики человека
доктор медицинских наук, профессор, академик АН РУз

Jin Young Choi

профессор департамента оральной и челюстно-лицевой
хирургии школы стоматологии Стоматологического
госпиталя Сеульского национального университета,
Президент Корейского общества челюстно-лицевой и
эстетической хирургии

Абдуллаева Наргиза Нурмаматовна

доктор медицинских наук, профессор, проректор
Самаркандского государственного медицинского
университета, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-7529-4248

Худоярова Дилдора Рахимовна

доктор медицинских наук, доцент, заведующая кафедрой
Акушерства и гинекологии №1 Самаркандского
государственного медицинского университета
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5770-2255

Орипов Фирдавс Суръатович

доктор медицинских наук, доцент, заведующий кафедрой
Гистологии, цитологии и эмбриологии Самаркандского
государственного медицинского университета
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-0615-0144

Мавлянов Фарход Шавкатович

доктор медицинских наук, доцент кафедры Детской
хирургии Самаркандского государственного медицинского
университета, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0003-2650-4445

Магзумова Наргиза Махкамовна

Доктор медицинских наук, профессор кафедры
акушерства и гинекологии Семейной медицины
Ташкентской медицинской академии
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9313-4918

Акбаров Миршавкат Миролимович

доктор медицинских наук,
Республиканский специализированный центр
хирургии имени академика В.Вахидова

Саидов Саидмир Абrorович

доктор медицинских наук, Ташкентский
фармацевтический институт
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6616-5428

Бабаджанов Ойбек Абдужаббарович

доктор медицинских наук, Ташкентский педиатрический
медицинский институт, кафедра Дерматовенерология, детская
дерматовенерология и СПИД, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-3022-916X

Теребаев Билим Алдамуратович

кандидат медицинских наук, доцент кафедры Факультетской
детской хирургии Ташкентского педиатрического
медицинского института.
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-5409-4327

Юлдашев Ботир Ахматович

кандидат медицинских наук, доцент кафедры Педиатрии,
неонатологии и протекции детских болезней №2
Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2442-1523

Ибрагимова Малика Худайбергеновна

доктор медицинских наук, профессор
Ташкентского государственного
стоматологического института
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9235-1742

Рахимов Нодир Махамматкулович

доктор медицинских наук, доцент кафедры
онкологии Самаркандского государственного
медицинского университета
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5272-5503

Верстка: Хуршид Мирзахмедов

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

Chief Editor:

Rizaev Jasur Alimjanovich
MD, DSc, Professor of Dental Medicine,
Rector of the Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5468-9403

Deputy Chief Editor:

Ziyadullaev Shukhrat Khudayberdievich
Doctor of Medical Sciences, Vice-Rector for scientific work
and Innovation, Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9309-3933

Responsible secretary:

Samieva Gulnoza Utkurovna
doctor of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor,
Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6142-7054

Responsible for publication:

Shakhanova Shakhnoza Shaykatovna
PhD Department of Oncology
Samarkand State medical university
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-0888-9150

EDITORIAL BOARD:

Aripova Tamara Uktamovna

*Director of the Institute of Immunology and Human Genomics -
Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Academician of the
Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan*

Jin Young Choi

*Professor Department of Oral and Maxillofacial
Surgery School of Dentistry Dental Hospital
Seoul National University, President of the
Korean Society of Maxillofacial Aesthetic Surgery*

Abdullaeva Nargiza Nurmatovna

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Vice-Rector
Samarkand State Medical University, Chief Physician of
the 1st Clinic **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-7529-4248*

Khudoyarova Dildora Rakhimovna

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor,
Head of the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology,
Samarkand State Medical University No.1
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5770-2255*

Oripov Firdavs Suratovich

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor,
Head of the Department of Histology, Cytology and
Embryology of Samarkand State Medical University.
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-0615-0144*

Mavlyanov Farkhod Shavkatovich

*Doctor of Medicine, Associate Professor of Pediatric
Surgery, Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2650-4445*

Magzumova Nargiza Makhamovna

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Department
of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Family Medicine,
Tashkent Medical Academy
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9313-4918*

Akbarov Mirshavkat Mirolimovich

*Doctor of Medical Sciences,
Republican Specialized Center of Surgery
named after academician V.Vakhidov*

Saidov Saidamir

*Doctor of Medical Sciences,
Tashkent Pharmaceutical Institute,
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6616-5428*

Babadjanov Oybek Abdujabbarovich

*Doctor of sciences in medicine, Tashkent Pediatric
Medical Institute, Department of Dermatovenerology,
pediatric dermatovenerology and AIDS
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-3022-916X*

Terebaev Bilim Aldamuratovich

*Candidate of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor,
Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute,
Faculty of Children Department of Surgery.
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-5409-4327.*

Yuldashev Botir Akhmatovich

*Candidate of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor of
Pediatrics, Neonatology and Propaedeutics of Pediatrics,
Samarkand State Medical University No. 2.
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2442-1523*

Ibragimova Malika Xudayberganovna

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor,
Tashkent State Dental Institute
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9235-1742*

Rahimov Nodir Maxammatkulovich

*DSc, Associate Professor of Oncology,
Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5272-5503*

Page Maker: Khurshid Mirzakhmedov

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

OBSTETRICS AND GYNECOLOGY

1. **Khudoyarova R. Dildora, Karabayeva A. Marjona**
THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE REACTIVITY OF THE AUTONOMIC NERVOUS SYSTEM AND THE BIRTH PROCESS IN WOMEN IN LABOR WITH THE NORMOCHROMIC TYPE OF BLOOD CIRCULATION.....10
2. **Karabayeva A. Marjona, Khudoyarova R. Dildora**
CHANGES IN THE MOTHER-PLACENTA-FETUS SYSTEM IN WOMEN IN LABOR WITH IRON DEFICIENCY ANEMIA WITH A MODERATE PREDOMINANCE OF THE TONE OF THE SYMPATHETIC NERVOUS SYSTEM.....17
3. **Tillabayeva M. Dilnoza**
DYSMENORRHEA IN ADOLESCENT GIRLS ON THE BACKGROUND OF POSTCOVOID SYNDROME.....23

HEALTHCARE

4. **Madazimov M. Madamin, Mamasoliev S. Nematjon, Botirov A. Jakhongir**
PREVENTIVE AND PREVENTIVE ISSUES OF CHOLECYSTITIS IN THE POPULATION OF DIFFERENT AGES, TOPICAL ISSUES AND MAIN PRIORITIES (LITERATURE REVIEW)31

THERAPY

5. **Tashkenbaeva N. Eleonora, Rakhmanov Kh. Bakhodir, Kholikov B. Ikhtiyor**
FACTORS ASSOCIATED WITH SYSTOLIC DYSFUNCTION OF THE RIGHT VENTRICLE IN PATIENTS WITH A HISTORY OF MYOCARDIAL INFARCTION41
6. **Akhmedova Sh.Nilufar, Makhmudov B.Ravshan**
RISK OF DEVELOPING CHRONIC KIDNEY DISEASE WITH OBESITY AND A MODERN APPROACH TO DIAGNOSIS.....51
7. **Karamatullaeva E. Zebo, Ibragimova F. Elnara**
THE ROLE OF BLOOD COAGULATION INDICATORS IN CORONAVIRUS INFECTION DISEASE.....57
8. **Khasanjanova O. Farida, Yorbulov S. Laziz**
EVALUATION OF THE EFFECT OF THE CARDIOPROTECTOR TRIMETAZIDINE ON THE CLINICAL COURSE OF MYOCARDIAL INFARCTION COMPLICATED BY CHRONIC HEART FAILURE IN YOUNG PATIENTS63
9. **Amirova A. Shokhidabonu**
STUDYING THE INFLUENCE OF SELECTIVE BETA-BLOCKERS ON 24-HOUR BLOOD PRESSURE MONITORING.....70

SURGERY

10. **Rakhmanov E. Kosim, Davlatov S. Salim, Radjabov P. Jasur**
ANALYSIS OF RELAPSE OF LIVER ECHINOCOCCOSIS AND THE ROLE OF MORPHOLOGICAL MODIFICATION.....76
11. **Aslanov G. Valijon, Xujabaev T. Safarboy**
DIFFERENTIATED SURGICAL TACTICS IN ACUTE ADHESIVE SMALL INTESTINAL OBSTRUCTION.....83
12. **Kurbaniyozov B. Zafar, Mukhiddinov X. Bobur, Askarov A. Pulat**
IMPROVEMENT OF MINIMALLY INVASIVE SURGICAL INTERVENTIONS IN THE TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH CHOLECYSTOCHOLEDOCHOLITHIASIS.....89

13. **Utayev H. Latifjon, Dusiyarov M. Muhammad, Askarov A. Pulat**
CLINICAL FEATURES OF STARGED VENTRAL HERNIA COMPLICATED WITH
INTESTINAL OBSTRUCTION.....95
14. **Sayinaev K. Farrukh, Kurbaniyazov B. Zafar, Rakhmanov E. Kasim**
COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE RESULTS OF SURGICAL TREATMENT OF
PATIENTS WITH POSTOPERATIVE VENTRAL HERNIAS103
15. **Ilkhomov E. Oybek**
CURRENT VIEWS ON MINOR INVASIVE CORONARY SURGERY.....111
16. **Rizaev A. E'zozbek, Kurbaniyazov B. Zafar, Abduraxmanov Sh. Diyor**
THE IMPORTANCE OF MINIMALLY INVASIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN ACUTE
PANCREATITIS SURGERY.....120
17. **Rizaev A. E'zozbek, Kurbaniyazov B. Zafar, Abduraxmanov Sh. Diyor**
PROGNOSIS OF THE SEVERITY OF ACUTE PANCREATITIS ACCORDING TO THE
RESULTS OF LAPAROSCOPY AND THE BALTHAZAR SCALE129

PEDIATRICS

18. **Devorova B. Marifat**
ETIOPATHOGENESIS, METHODS OF TREATMENT AND PREVENTION OF FOOD
ALLERGIES IN CHILDREN.....139
19. **Ibatova M. Shoir, Abdullaeva E. Mavjuda, Mamatkulova Kh. Dilrabo**
SOME ASPECTS OF PNEUMONIA IN YOUNG CHILDREN145
20. **Ibatova M. Shoir, Mamatkulova Kh. Feruza**
SOME ASPECTS OF GIARDIASIS IN CHILDREN.....151

CHILDREN SURGERY

21. **Abdullaev B. Zafar, Agzamkhodjaev T. Saidanvar**
CONTEMPORARY COMPLEX TREATMENT OF BLADDER EXSTROPHY IN
CHILDREN.....157
22. **Ollabergenov T. Odilbek, Terebaev A. Bilim, Nematov Sh. Alisher**
TRANSANAL ENDORECTAL SURGERY BY DE LA TORRE MONDRAGON AS A
METHOD OF CHOICE IN YOUNG CHILDREN WITH HIRSCHSPRUNG'S DISEASE.169

DENTISTRY AND MAXILLOFACIAL SURGERY

23. **Indiaminova N. Gavkhar**
ASSESSMENT OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF TEETH FISSURAL SEALING IN THE
PREVENTION OF CARIES OF PERMANENT TEETH IN CHILDREN WITH DAUN
SYNDROME.....176

OTORHINOLARYNGOLOGY

24. **Omonova Sh. Maftuna, Nasretdinova T. Makhzuna**
EFFICIENCY OF MICROWAVE IMMUNOMODULATION DURING SPECIFIC
HYPOSENSIBILIZATION IN PATIENTS WITH POLLINOSIS.....184
25. **Nasretdinova T. Makhzuna, Makhkamova E. Nigora, Usmanova A. Nilufar,
Normuradov A. Nodirjon**
ASSESSMENT OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF ENDOSCOPIC ADENOTOMY AND
MYRINGOTOMY IN PATIENTS WITH EXUDATIVE OTITIS MEDIA AND AUDITORY
TUBE DYSFUNCTION189

26. **Makhkamova E. Nigora, Nabiyeva M. Djamila**
DIAGNOSIS OF PATHOLOGY OF THE NASAL CAVITY AND PARANASAAL SINUSES
IN CHILDREN WITH CONGENITAL CLEFT LIP AND PALATE.....197

PSYCHONEUROLOGY

27. **Khakimova Z. Sokhiba, Kodirov A. Umid, Mukhammadiyeva Dilafruz**
THE RESULTS OF EXAMINATION AND EFFECTIVENESS OF TREATMENT IN
PATIENTS SUFFERING WITH PAIN SYNDROME WITH COMPRESSION-ISCHEMIC
DORSOPATHY.....209
28. **Khakimova Z. Sokhiba, Kodirov A. Umid, Fayzullayev Ganisher**
RESULTS OF CLINICAL AND NEUROLOGICAL INDICATIONS IN PATIENTS WITH
LUMBAR DORSOPATHY OF RHEUMATIC ORIGIN.....216
29. **Mirdjurayev M. Elbek, Adambayev I. Zufar, Samiyev S. Asliddin, Ergashev B. G'ulom**
MODERN PROBLEMS OF DORSALGIA IN MODIC TYPE SPONDYLODISCITIS.....223
30. **Turaev M. Tolib, Kuchimova A. Charos**
CLINICAL ASPECTS OF ANXIETY-PANIC DISORDERS IN EPILEPSY.....230
31. **Mamatqurbonov B. Shokirjon**
FEATURES OF CLINICAL AND NEUROLOGICAL DISORDERS IN EPILEPSY IN
RESIDENTS OF MOUNTAIN AND DESERT AREAS.....235
32. **Mamatqurbonov B. Shokirjon**
FEATURES OF NEUROVISUALIZATION DISORDERS IN IDIOPATHIC AND
SYMPTOMATIC EPILEPSY IN RESIDENTS OF MOUNTAIN AND DESERT AREAS,
CONSIDERING THE CSF CRANIAL INDEX.....245

ONCOLOGY AND RADIOLOGY

33. **Yusupbekov A. Abror., Tillyashaykhova M. Rano, Tuychiyev P. Anvar**
DEVELOPMENT OF THERAPEUTIC AND DIAGNOSTIC TACTICS FOR NON-
MUSCLE-INVASIVE BLADDER CANCER USING MINIMALLY INVASIVE
TECHNOLOGIES.....255
34. **Rakhimov M. Nodir, Shakhanova Sh. Shakhnoza**
SARCOPENIA THROUGH THE EYES OF AN ONCOLOGIST AND RADIATION
DIAGNOSTIC METHODS.....266
35. **Akramov R. Akhtam**
DRUG THERAPY OF MALIGNANT TUMORS (CHEMOTHERAPY, TARGETED
THERAPY, IMMUNOTHERAPY).....275

MORPHOLOGY

36. **Khamidova M. Farida, Nurullayev A. Javohir**
ON THE ISSUE OF MORPHOLOGICAL FEATURES OF KERATODERMA IN
DIABETES MELLITUS284
37. **Khamidova M. Farida, Ruzikulov Zh. Sobir**
GENETIC ASPECTS OF NEWBORN RESPIRATORY DISTRESS SYNDROME.....292
38. **Abdirashidova A. Gulnoza, Gafurov A. Farrukh**
PATHOPHYSIOLOGY MECHANISMS OF OBESITY IN TYPE I DIABETES.....299
39. **Usanov S. Sanjar, Abduraimov A. Zafarjan**
MORPHOLOGY AND MORPHOMETRIC CHARACTERISTICS OF LIVER TISSUE OF
GROUP FIFTH WHITE RATS305

40. **Toshmamatov N. Bakhtiyor, Djumanova E. Nargiza**
CHANGES IN THE MORPHOLOGICAL AND MORPHOMETRIC PARAMETERS OF THE GASTRIC WALL IN POLYPRAGMASS WITH ANTI-INFLAMMATORY DRUGS.....312
41. **Ergashev S. Suhrob S., Niyozov T. Shuhrat, Djurabekova T. Aziza**
ANALYSIS OF THE EFFECTS OF PERINATAL HYPOXIA IN ANIMAL EXPERIMENTS.....318

TRAUMATOLOGY AND ORTHOPEDICS

42. **Rizaev J. Alimdjanovich, Khusainboev Sh., Davronbekovich**
SYMPTOMS, CAUSES AND TREATMENTS FOR SHOULDER INJURIES (LITERATURE REVIEW)324
43. **Rizaev J. Alimdjanovich, Khusainboev Sh., Davronbekovich**
MODERN ASPECTS OF THE DIAGNOSIS OF OVERWORK SYNDROME IN ROWERS.....331
44. **Axtamov A'zam, Axtamov A. Azim, Raxmonov N. Temur**
CONSERVATIVE TREATMENT OF CONGENITAL CLUBFOOT IN INFANTS (LITERATURE REVIEW).....337
45. **Axtamov A'zam, Axtamov A. Azim**
THE ROLE OF BREASTFEEDING NEWBORNS.....346
46. **Mamatkulov Kh. Oybek, Khusainboev D. Shokhrukhbek**
KNEE JOINT INJURIES DURING SPORTS.....354
47. **Kholkhudjayev I. Farrukh, Onorboyev A. Dilmurod**
RESULTS OF ARTHROSCOPIC PARTIAL MENISCECTOMY.....362
48. **Kholkhudjayev I. Farrukh, Onorboyev A. Dilmurod**
RESULTS OF PLASTY OF THE ANTERIOR CRUCIATE LIGAMENT USING THE HAMSTRING TENDONS.....368
49. **Eranov N. Sherzod, Eranov F. Nurali, Kholkhudjayev I. Farrukh**
ANATOMICAL STRUCTURE OF THE DISTAL PART OF THE CARPAL BONES IN CHILDREN AND CHARACTERISTICS OF INJURIES.....374

FORENSIC MEDICAL EXAMINATION

50. **Indiaminov I. Sayit, Shoimov U. Shukrillo**
EPIDEMIOLOGY AND MEDICAL AND SOCIAL ASPECTS OF MODERN ROAD TRANSPORT INJURIES AND VEHICLE INJURIES (LITERATURE REVIEW).....382
51. **Olimova M. Madinabonu**
COMPARISON OF ROAD TRANSPORT ACCIDENTS IN UZBEKISTAN AND RUSSIA.....389
52. **Beknazarov Y. Shokir, Khasanova A. Mukarrama., Beknazarov Sh. Jahongir**
PRACTICAL IMPORTANCE OF SCIENTIFIC WORKS OF SCIENTISTS OF MEDICAL UNIVERSITIES OF NEW UZBEKISTAN IN THE FIELD OF PHYSICAL EVIDENCE OF FORENSIC MEDICAL EXAMINATION QUALITY398

INFECTIOUS DISEASES

53. **Ergasheva Ya. Munisa, Yarmukhamedova A. Nargiza, Mallakhodjayev A. Anvarkhon**
ROLE OF ENTEROVIRAL INFECTION IN THE FORMATION OF SEROUS MENINGITIS.....404
54. **Rizayev A. Jasur, Ergasheva Ya. Munisa**
IMPACT OF THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC ON CHILDREN WITH DISABILITIES410

55. **Djuraeva S. Kamola, Niyazova A. Tajigul**
CLINICAL AND IMMUNOLOGICAL FEATURES OF THE COURSE OF BRUCELLOSIS
IN WOMEN OF FERTILE AGE.....418
56. **Achilova M. Matlyuba. Bayjanov K. Allabergan, Yarmuxamedova A. Nargiza**
INFLUENCE OF ANTI-PROTOZAL THERAPY ON THE NUMBER OF CD4+
LYMPHOCYTES IN HIV INFECTION WITH HYAMBLYOSIS AND
BLASTOCYSTOSIS.....428
57. **Karamatullaeva E. Zebo**
FEATURES OF THE COURSE OF SEROUS MENINGITIS OF MUMPS ETIOLOGY IN
ADULTS (ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE SAMARKAND REGION).....435
58. **Rustamova A. Shahlo, Vafokulova Kh. Nargiza**
THE EFFECT OF CESAREAN SECTION ON THE INTESTINAL MICROFLORA IN
NEWBORNS IN THE SAMARKAND REGION.....443

DERMATOVENEROLOGY

59. **Rizaev A. Jasur, Imamov S. Otabek, Abduvakhitova N. Indira**
ROLE OF ENDOGENOUS INTOXICATION IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF HERPES-
ASSOCIATED EXUDATIVE ERYTHEMA MULTIFORME.....451
60. **Khamidova M. Farida, Khusinova A. Firuza**
GENETIC FACTORS OF ACNE.....457

БИОМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

ЖУРНАЛ БИОМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ | JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE

УДК:616.711-007.1-073.75

КНАКИМОВА Sahiba Ziyadulloyevna
Doctor of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor
КОДИРОВ Umid Arzikulovich
ФАЙЗУЛЛАЕВ Ganisher
Samarkand State Medical University

RESULTS OF CLINICAL AND NEUROLOGICAL INDICATIONS IN PATIENTS WITH LUMBAR DORSOPATHY OF RHEUMATIC ORIGIN

For citation: Khakimova Z. Sokhiba, Kodirov A. Umid, Fayzullayev Ganisher. Results of clinical and neurological indications in patients with lumbar dorsopathy of rheumatic origin // Journal of Biomedicine and Practice. 2024, vol. 9, issue 4, pp.216-222

 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13710061>

ABSTRACT

We selected 35 patients of group 3 with dorsopathies of rheumatic origin: 10 (28.5) - men, 25 (71.5%) - women. The distribution of patients in age groups was as follows: under 19 years - 3 people; 19-29 - 7 people; 30-39 years old - 11 people; 40-49 - 10 people; 50-59 years old - 3 people; Over 60 years old - 1 person. The average age of the patients was 39 years. We also analyzed the causes of diseases whose etiology is very complex and at the same time very simple.

Key words: rheumatic dorsopathy, ischioradiculalgia, chronic dorsopathy, osteochondrosis, streptococcus.

ХАКИМОВА Сахиба Зиядуллоевна
доктор медицинских наук, доцент
КОДИРОВ Умид Арзикулович
ФАЙЗУЛЛАЕВ Ганишер

Самаркандский государственный медицинский университет

РЕЗУЛЬТАТЫ КЛИНИКО-НЕВРОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ПОКАЗАНИЙ У БОЛЬНЫХ ПОЯСНИЧНОЙ ДОРСОПАТИЕЙ РЕВМАТИЧЕСКОГО ПРОИСХОЖДЕНИЯ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Мы выбрали 35 пациентов 3-й группы с дорсопатиями ревматического генеза: 10 (28,5) - мужчин, 25 (71,5%) - женщин. Распределение больных по возрастным группам было следующим: до 19 лет - 3 человека; 19-29 - 7 человек; 30-39 лет - 11 человек; 40-49 - 10 человек; 50-59 лет - 3 человека; Старше 60 лет - 1 человек. Средний возраст пациентов составил 39 лет. Мы также проанализировали причины заболеваний, этиология которых очень сложна и в то же время очень проста.

Ключевые слова: ревматическая дорсопатия, ишиорадикулоалгия, хроническая дорсопатия, остеохондроз, стрептококк.

XAKIMOVA Soxiba Ziyadulloyevna

Tibbiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent,

KODIROV Umid Arzikulovich

FAYZULLAYEV Ganisher

Samarqand davlat tibbiyot universiteti

РЕВМАТИК KELIB CHIQISHLI BEL UMURTQALARI DORSOPATIYASI BO'LGAN BEMORLARDA KLINIK VA NEVROLOGIK KO'RSATKICHLARNING NATIJALARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Biz revmatik kelib chiqishi dorsopatiyalari bo'lgan 3-guruhdagi 35 nafar bemorni tanladik: 10 (28,5) - erkaklar, 25 (71,5%) - ayollar. Yosh guruhlarida bemorlarning taqsimlanishi quyidagicha edi: 19 yoshgacha - 3 kishi; 19-29 – 7 kishi; 30-39 yosh - 11 kishi; 40-49 - 10 kishi; 50-59 yosh - 3 kishi; 60 yoshdan oshgan - 1 kishi. Bemorlarning o'rtacha yoshi 39 yoshni tashkil etdi. Biz, shuningdek, etiologiyasi juda murakkab va shu bilan birga juda oddiy bo'lgan kasalliklarning sabablarini tahlil qildik.

Kalit so'zlar: revmatik dorsopatiya, isxioradikuloalgiya, surunkali dorsopatiya, osteoxondroz, streptokokk.

Kirish. Vizual analog shkalasi bo'yicha og'riq darajasi (mm) kunduzi o'rtacha intensivlikdagi og'riqni yengillashtiruvchi og'riq va kechasi kuchli og'riq intensivligiga ega edi. Neyrovizual kuzatuvda bemorlarda quyidagilar aniqlandi: intervertebral disklarning tashqi qatlamlarining ossifikatsiyasi, suyak ko'priklarining shakllanishi, spondilodiskit shaklida intervertebral disklarning yallig'lanish belgilari

Tadqiqot usullari: Revmatik kelib chiqishi dorsopatiyasining rivojlanishida asosiy rol streptokokk infeksiyasiga tegishli (b-gemolitik streptokokklar guruhi). Kasallikning rivojlanishida bemorda immunitetning buzilishi katta ahamiyatga ega jarayonning rivojlanishining patogenezi ikkita asosiy omil bilan belgilanadi: streptokokklar tomonidan ishlab chiqarilgan, neyrotoksik xususiyatlarga ega bo'lgan bir qator fermentlarning toksik ta'siri va streptokokkning ayrim shtammlarida asab to'qimalari bilan umumiy antigenik determinantlarning mavjudligi.

1-rasm. Bemorlarning jinsi va yoshi bo'yicha taqsimlanishi.

Revmatik kelib chiqadigan dorsopatiya tajribasi 2,5 yilni tashkil etdi. Quyidagi rasmda ushbu kasallikka olib keladigan qo'zg'atuvchi omillar keltirilgan. Eng muhim qo'zg'atuvchi omil irsiy moyillik edi (anamnezda aniqlangan), bu 23 (67,1%) bemorni tashkil etdi. Shuningdek, kasallikning boshlanishi uchun qo'zg'atuvchi omillar gipotermiya - 13 (38,1%), stress - 7 (21%), oldingi infeksiyalar (sitomegalovirus, mikoplazma, herpes virusi, qizilcha) - 5 (14,5%).

2-rasm. Revmatik kelib chiqishi surunkali dorsopatiya rivojlanishiga sabab bo'lgan asosiy omillar

Tadqiqot natijalari: Fizikal tekshiruvi shuni ko'rsatdiki, umumiy ko'rikda teri rangi oqargan, teri osti yog'i qavati kam rivojlangan. Limfa tugunlarining kattalashishi, suyak deformatsiyasi yo'q. Pulsning o'rtacha tezligi daqiqada 89,9 zarbani tashkil etdi, ya'ni taxikardiyaga moyillik bor edi.

Tadqiqotda ishtirok etgan barcha bemorlar shuni ko'rsatdilar: vosita va hissiy buzilishlar, ko'proq oyoq-qo'llarda proksimal qismida og'riqlar, vegetativ-qon tomir ko'rinishlardagi o'zgarishlar sodir bo'ldi. Subyektiv va ob'ektiv simptomlarning statistik tahlili ushbu rasmda keltirilgan. Kun davomida vizual analog shkalasi bo'yicha og'riq sindromi 34 dan 65 gacha va o'rtacha 51,9 ni tashkil etdi. Kechasi bemorlarni yanada kuchliroq og'riq bezovta qildi, bu yerda vizual analog shkalasi qiymatlari 45 dan 85 gacha, o'rtacha 68,5 ni tashkil etdi. Ko'pchilik bemorlar 30 (84,5%) bel soxasidagi og'riqdan shikoyat qildilar.

3-rasm. Bemorlarda asosiy shikoyatlarning paydo bo'lish chastotasi, %da.

Bemorlarni mushaklar va bo'g'imlardagi og'riqlarning o'zgaruvchanligi - 15 (42,1%), fibromialgiya - 22 (63,1%), ertalabki charchoq xissi - 21 (61,8%) kuzatildi.

1-jadval.

Bemorlarda asosiy shikoyatlarning paydo bo'lish chastotasi

Simptom	Jami (N=35)	
	abs	%
oyoq-qo'lning distal zonasida sezuvchanlikning pasayishi	25	72.4
uyqusizlik hissi	17	47.4
oyoq-qo'llardagi harakatlarni cheklash	19	56.6
mushak atrofiyasi	20	57,9
tendon reflekslarining pasayishi	17	48,7
vegetativ-qon tomir kasalliklari	19	55.3
Orqa miya rentgenogrammasi: oldingi spondilit,umurtqa tanasining destruktiv bo'lmagan sklerozi, umurtqa osteoporoz	24	68,4
Orqa miya MRT va MsKT	11	31.6

Ko'pgina bemorlar tananing turli qismlarida tez-tez og'riyotgan, uzoq davom etadigan og'riqlardan shikoyat qildilar, ular buni quyidagicha ta'rifladilar: kuyushuvchi, chimchilovchi, zaiflashtiruvchi va monoton.

4-rasm. Bemorlarda surunkali og'riqni lokalizatsiya qilish.

Boshqa guruhlardagi bemorlardan og'riqning o'ziga xosligi sovuq va nam havoda, asabiylashganda va stressda og'riqning kuchayishi edi. Iliq xonada, ayniqsa saunalarda og'riq kamaygan, ammo keyinchalik yana kuchayganligi aniqlandi. Bemorning doimiy zaiflashuv holati tez-tez kayfiyat o'zgarishiga olib keladi - 26 (73,7%).

Revmatik genezli dorsopatiyalarida nevrologik holat asosiy kasallikka xos belgilarni aniqladi: sezuvchanlik, asosan, oyoq-qo'lning distal zonasida kamaydi - 25 (72,4%); uyqusizlik hissi - 17 (47,4%), sovuqotishlik va oyoq-qo'llarda harakatlarning cheklanishi - 20 (56,6%), tendon reflekslarining pasayishi - 17 (48,7%). Harorat sezgirligi asosan sovuq reaksiyaga giperesteziyani ko'rsatdi. Mushaklar kuchini saqlab qolgan holda, tebranish va nerv mushak patologiya ko'rinishidagi chuqur sezuvchanlik aniqlanmadi. Muhim alomatlardan biri gipergidroz, rangparlik va sovuq barmoqlar va oyoq barmoqlari shaklida vegetativ-qon tomir kasalliklari edi.

Oswestry so'rovnomasiga ko'ra, minimal ball 38%, maksimal - 58% va o'rtacha 50% edi.

Uchinchi guruh bemorlaridagi so'rovnomaga faol hayot (jinsiy hayot o'rniga), shuningdek, gipotermiya (bo'sh vaqt o'rniga) tahliliga oid quyidagi moslashtirilgan savollardan iborat edi. Olingan ko'rsatkichlar juda aniq og'riqni ko'rsatdi, uning o'ziga xos xususiyati mushaklar va bo'g'imlarning o'zgaruvchanligi, shuningdek, tez-tez uyg'onish bilan yuzaki uyqu, bu doimo charchagan bemorning ertalablari zaiflik hissi paydo bo'lishiga olib keldi. Shuningdek, so'rovnomaga atrofdagi haroratning pasayishi bilan vaziyatning yomonlashishini va aksincha, o'sish bilan yaxshilanishini ko'rsatdi.

24 (68,4%) bemorda umurtqa pog'onasi rentgenografiyasi: oldingi spondilit; umurtqali jismlarning buzilmaydigan sklerozi, umurtqa pog'onasining osteoporozi, umurtqa pog'onasining notekis bo'g'im yuzalari.

5-rasm. Bemorlarning neyrovizual tadqiqotlari natijalari

Ko'pgina bemorlar tananing turli qismlarida tez-tez og'riyotgan, uzoq davom etadigan og'riqlardan shikoyat qildilar, ular buni quyidagicha ta'rifladilar: yonish, chimchilash, zaiflashtiruvchi va monoton. Boshqa guruhlardagi bemorlardan og'riqning o'ziga xos omili sovuq va nam havoda, qoralama va stressda og'riqning kuchayishi edi. Iliq xonada, ayniqsa saunalarda og'riq kamaygan, ammo keyinchalik yana kuchayganligi aniqlandi. Bemorning doimiy zaiflashgan holati tez-tez kayfiyat o'zgarishiga olib keladi. Revmatik kelib chiqishi dorsopatiyalari bilan surunkali og'riqlar asosan artikulyar xarakterga ega, shuning uchun o'ziga xos antirevmatik terapiya fonida NSAIDlar, miorelaksant va antidepressantlar buyuriladi.

Xulosa: Orqa miya degenerativ kasalliklari vaqt o'tishi bilan rivojlanadigan kaskadli jarayon ekanligi ko'rsatilgan. Klinik ko'rinishlar murakkab o'zgarishlar, jumladan, osteoxondroz, spondiloz, osteoartrit tufayli yuzaga keladi, ular ko'pincha tug'ma moyillik bilan kuchayadi. Shunday qilib, bu guruhdagi bemorlarning klinik va nevrologik tadqiqoti natijalari shuni ko'rsatdiki, bel mintaqadagi surunkali og'riqlar og'riqli xarakterga ega, mushaklar va bo'g'imlarda og'riqning o'zgaruvchanligi, fibromiyalgiya, shuningdek, tez-tez yuzaki uyqu bilan charchagan bemorlar. uyg'onishlar, bu ertalab zaiflik hissi paydo bo'lishiga olib keldi.

IQTIBOSLAR | ЧОККИ | REFERENCES:

1. Khamdamova B.K., Khakimova S.Z., Kodirov U.A. Features of the neurovascular state of the spine in dorsopathies in patients with diabetes mellitus // Journal of Biomedicine and Practice. – 2022. – vol. 7. – No. 6. (in Russ)

2. Khakimova S.Z., Atokhodjaeva D.A., Hamrokulova F.M. Research Of Motor Function In Patients With Chronic Pain Syndrome At Radiculopathies Of Different Genesis. The American Journal of Applied sciences, 2020. 2 (10), 14-21.
3. Khakimova S.Z., Khamdamova B.K., Kodirov U.O. Comparative correlation of markers of inflammatory metamorphism in peripheral blood in dorsopathies of various origins //Uzbek journal of case reports. – 2022. 2(2). 12-18. (in Russ).
4. Samiyev A.S, Xakimova S.X, Soibnazarov O.E. Rehabilitation of patients under spine surger. Journal of Biomedicine and Practice. 2022;7(1):139-44.
5. Utkurovna S.G., Farkhodovna, K.F., Orifjonovna O.F, Features of immune mechanisms in the development of pathological processes,2022 ,2 (82), 108-115.
6. Axmedova D.A., Xakimova S.Z., Djurabekova A.T. " Features of post-stroke depression in the early and late recovery periods" Innovative Science, 2015, 6(2), 224-227 (in Russ).
7. Burieva D.M., Xakimova S.Z., Djurabekova A.T. " Comparative study of the function of maintaining a vertical posture in healthy foxes and patients with parkinsonism" Innovative science, 2015. 6(2) 232-236 (in Russ).
8. Dadasheva M.N., Razilova A.V., Boldin A.V. Possibilities of practical use of dexketoprofen in pain syndrome of various etiologies. 2018. 16(10),32–36. (in Uzb).
9. Khamdamova B.K., Khakimova S.Z., Kodirov U.A. Features of the neurovascular state of the spine in dorsopathies in patients with diabetes mellitus // Journal of Biomedicine and Practice.2022.7(6). (in Russ).
10. Khakimova S.Z., Khamdamova B.K., Kodirov U.A. Features of clinical and neurological results of examination of patients with dorsopathies of rheumatic origin // Journal of Biomedicine and Practice. – 2022. 7(1). (in Russ).
11. Khakimova S.Z., Khamdamova B. K., Kodirov U.A. Study of motor function in patients with chronic pain syndrome with dorsopathies of various origins // tools, mechanisms and technologies of modern innovative development. – 2022. 243-251. (in Russ).
12. Khakimova S.Z. Chronic brucelosis in the real practice of a neurologist: (clinical diagnosis and treatment). Benefits of clinical and experimental medicine, 2019;1 (3), 133–138. (in Russ).
13. Rizaev Zh. A., Khaidarov N. K. Clinical , epidemiological and etiopathogenetic study of ischemic stroke // Journal of Neurology and Neurosurgical Research. – 2020. – Т. 1. – No. 1.
14. Abdullayev Afzal, Kubayev Aziz, Rizayev Jasur . Excitability threshold in neuritis of the lower alveolar nerve. Journal of Biomedicine and Practice. 2022, vol. 7, issue 4, pp.238-245
15. Rizaev , Zh., Raimova , M., Boboev , K., & Abdullaeva, M. (2019). Parkinson's: classification, clinical picture and basics of treatment. Stomatologiya , 1(1(74), 64–67
16. ShSh Shakhanova , NM Rakhimov. Multimodal approach to the treatment of multiple osteogenic metastases of kidney and prostate cancer . Clinical and Experimental Oncology 2020, No. 4 Page 50-56.

Статья поступила в редакцию 11.07.2024; одобрена после рецензирования 21.08.2024; принята к публикации 24.08.2024.

The article was submitted 11.07.2024; approved after reviewing 21.08.2024; accepted for publication 24.08.2024.

Информация об авторах:

Хакимова Сохиба Зиядуллоевна — д.м.н., заведующая кафедрой неврологии факультета последипломного образования Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета, Самарканд, Узбекистан. <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4804-3651>

Файзуллаев Ганишер- Клинический ординатор кафедры неврологии факультета последипломного образования Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета, Самарканд, Узбекистан. <https://orcid.org/0009-0004-3547-1125>

Кодиров Умид Арзикулович — ассистент кафедры неврологии факультета последипломного образования Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета, Самарканд, Узбекистан <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9671-3288>

Источники финансирования: Работа не имела специального финансирования.

Конфликт интересов: Авторы декларируют отсутствие явных и потенциальных конфликтов интересов, связанных с публикацией настоящей статьи.

Вклад авторов:

Хакимова С З. — идеологическая концепция работы, редактирование статьи;

Файзуллаев Г.— сбор и анализ источников литературы, написание текста.

Кодиров У А. — сбор и анализ источников литературы, написание текста.

Information about the authors:

Khakimova Sokhiba Ziyadullaeva — doctor of medical sciences, head at the department of neurology of the faculty of postgraduate education of Samarkand state medical university, Samarkand, Uzbekistan. <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4804-3651>

Fayzullayev Ganisher- clinical ordinator of the department of neurology, faculty of postgraduate education, Samarkand State Medical University, Samarkand, Uzbekistan. <https://orcid.org/0009-0004-3547-1125>

Kodirov Umid Arzikulovich — teacher at the department of neurology of the faculty of postgraduate education of Samarkand state medical university, Samarkand, Uzbekistan. <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9671-3288>

Sources of funding: The work did not receive any specific funding.

Conflict of interest: The authors declare no explicit or potential conflicts of interest associated with the publication of this article.

Contribution of the authors:

Khakimova S Z — ideological concept of the work, editing the article;

Fayzullayev G— collection and analysis of literature sources, writing the text.

Kodirov U A — collection and analysis of literature sources, writing the text.

БИМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

9 ЖИЛД, 4 СОН

ЖУРНАЛ БИМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ

ТОМ 9, НОМЕР 4

JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE

VOLUME 9, ISSUE 4

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000